

DESCRIPTION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPED BASED ON EDUCATIONAL VALUES AND ITS MAIN PRINCIPLES

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Abstract: This article examines the methodology and theoretical-methodological foundations of preparing students for professional-pedagogical activities based on educational values. Additionally, it analyzes the description and main principles of pedagogical technology developed on the basis of an axiological approach.

Keywords: axiological approach, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, value, value-based approach, axiological hierarchy, technology, cognitive, emotional, sociocentric, genetic, national, historical, technological.

INTRODUCTION. The person-oriented approach, relying on the unity of psychological characteristics that constitute an individual's personality, implements the important psychological and pedagogical principle of an individualized approach with its own technology. According to this, the specific characteristics of each student are taken into account during lessons and training sessions. All of this creates optimal conditions that contribute to the development of the learner's personality through the leading educational activities of youth. To prepare students for professional pedagogical activity based on an axiological approach, it is first necessary to form an axiological need for pedagogical activity, enable them to understand national needs, exert influence, and improve value-based pedagogical activity aimed at this process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The socio-philosophical and pedagogical-psychological foundations of preparing students for professional activity and developing a system of values in Uzbekistan have been studied by scholars such as N. Shodiev, B. Adizov, O. Jamoldinova, I. Isaev, Sh. Mardonov, U. Makhkamov, O. Musurmonova, S. Nishonova, V. Slastenin, D. Ruzieva, B. Khodjaev, Sh. Sharipov, Sh. Shodmonova, E. Shiyanov, N. Egamberdieva, and M. Kuranov. In their scientific research, special attention has been paid to revealing the content and essence of national, universal, spiritual-moral, aesthetic, educational, and upbringing values, as well as the specific aspects of developing a system of values in future teachers.

A number of scientific studies have been conducted in CIS countries on preparing teachers for professional-pedagogical activities, designing the

educational process, and implementing it in education. In particular, this is reflected in the research of scholars such as O.A. Kolesnik, B.T. Likhacheva, A.I. Mishchenko, V.A. Slastenin, L.F. Spirina, L.G. Semushina, V.P. Bespalko, V.M. Monakhov, G.L. Ilyin, T.K. Smikovskaya, S.V. Vasekin, O.B. Yepisheva, and G.A. Monakhov.

Foreign scholars B. Wilson, J. Kim, Angela Stoff, Benjamin Bloom, Brian Cole, Drapeau Patty, Jaslin Holberg, Merriembar Jeron, and Leyla M. Spencer have examined the specific characteristics of developing readiness for professional-pedagogical activity among teaching staff. M. Spencer examined the characteristics of the formation of readiness for professional-pedagogical activity among teaching staff.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Person-centered technologies form the basis of a person-centered approach. It is founded on the following key principles.

The communicative foundation of person-centered technologies in the pedagogical process is a "new perspective on the learner," that is, a humanistic-personal approach, which includes:

- in the pedagogical process, the individual is not an object, but a subject;
- each learner is talented, and most are gifted;
- high ethical values (generosity, love, diligence, conscience, etc.) are considered the priority qualities of the individual.

The democratization of relationships in the educational process (teacher-learner, learner-learner) includes:

- equalizing the rights of the learner and the teacher, the learner's right to free choice;

- the right to make mistakes;

- the right to have one's own point of view should be the foundation of the relationship between the teacher and the learner, namely:

- a) not prohibiting;
- b) collaborating rather than controlling;
- c) persuading, not coercing;
- d) organizing, not ordering;
- e) allowing free choice, not imposing constraints.

The content of the aforementioned new relationships demonstrates the appropriateness of utilizing pedagogy that yields fewer results in suitable contexts within the current rapidly developing environment.

In our country, the goal of nurturing spiritually and physically mature youth and improving the quality of providing them with modern knowledge to develop

well-rounded individuals for society has been set as a priority in the field of education and upbringing. All actions taken in the process of continuous education are factors in achieving this goal. Currently, optimal methods for teaching all subjects based on modern pedagogical technologies are being investigated. In particular, the emergence of the national model of pedagogical technology and its gradual continuation in the form of providing knowledge based on preliminary design of educational activities is considered one of the innovations in the field of education. However, it should be emphasized that pedagogical technology did not appear yesterday or today; rather, each historical period had its own methods of education and upbringing, its own pedagogical technology. These developed as human spiritual and material needs increased.

As innovative pedagogical technologies are a necessary part of the education and upbringing system, they can bring about fundamental changes in the field of education. Education is the main idea that forms the basis of enlightenment, which includes understanding the connection between nature and society, rejecting authoritarian and false thinking methods, and developing qualities such as patience, contentment, respect for others' opinions, and cherishing national and universal values. The solution to this issue is closely linked to the technologization of education to a certain extent.

It is possible to achieve the intended goal by incorporating the teachings of our ancestors and our people's national values into the content of education and upbringing, and by applying modern pedagogical technologies to the educational process. At present, the flow of information is rapidly entering the social life of society and encompassing many spheres. The education system's necessary tasks can be defined as accelerating the reception, analysis, processing, theoretical generalization, summarization, and delivery of information. The application of pedagogical technologies in the educational process serves to positively address the aforementioned issues.

In reality, innovative pedagogical technology is quite complex and represents a modern approach that incorporates the best aspects of previous teaching methods. In innovative pedagogical technology, a project plan for activities to be carried out during lessons and training sessions is prepared in advance, with precise stages and timing. The project outlines key concepts, assessment questions, tools, and didactic materials to be used during the lesson. Students' ability to perform practical exercises and their overall mastery are continuously monitored. The implementation of innovative pedagogical

technologies in the educational process ensures that it is carried out at a good or excellent level, as the planned lesson projects are developed by scholars or experienced educators. Because planned lesson plans are developed by scientists or experienced educators.

Applying innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process requires creativity, knowledge, and experience from the teacher.

It was determined that lessons should be based on didactic principles, rules, a systematic approach, and pedagogical technology principles. When creating the project, it reflected what knowledge is acquired at which point, which didactic laws, rules, and principles are followed in the process of acquiring it, which types and stages of lessons, methods, information technologies, and didactic materials are used in the learning process.

The teacher's preparation for the lesson occurs in two stages.

1. General preparation for the lesson. The teacher's general preparation for the lesson is an ongoing process that includes:

Studying the state educational standard, qualification requirements, core curriculum, subject curricula, and their accompanying explanatory notes;

Regularly familiarizing oneself with new scientific and methodological literature on the subject;

Collecting new information in their field, compiling problem-based questions and assignments, and test materials;

Correctly selecting and appropriately using visual materials and teaching aids that can be employed in each lesson;

Continuously expanding one's knowledge by studying advanced pedagogical practices;

Improving skills in using information technologies during lessons, effectively utilizing electronic textbooks, text editors, and information posted on the internet.

2. Daily preparation for the lesson. The teacher's daily preparation ensures the organization of the lesson and the extent to which students acquire the knowledge, skills, and abilities imparted to them. The algorithm for preparing for the lesson (a set of rules) should be a consistent measure that takes into account and guarantees all factors and situations. Therefore, the teacher must follow these recommendations when preparing for each lesson:

The lesson places a great responsibility on the teacher. Thus, thorough preparation for each lesson is equally important for both experienced and

novice teachers. This requires a comprehensive study of each learner's personality, as it is the foundation for achieving the intended goal.

The implementation of students' professional training is carried out in accordance with the phased development of each course.

During the stage of realizing the teacher's status (first year), a holistic development is observed related to the individual's new social role and mastery of the profession's general scientific foundations. A person is distinguished by their adaptability to others' influence. During this period, students typically do not differentiate their roles. They become acquainted with specific forms of community life, establish new social connections, and adapt to different conditions. At this stage, students establish new social connections and adapt to different conditions.

In the professional self-awareness stage (second year), the specialized development of the student's personality continues, and their cultural demands and needs are formed. They gain confidence and independence, participating not only in all forms of education and upbringing but also actively in public organizations. During this period, attention is primarily focused on general professional disciplines.

At the professional self-realization stage (third year), students' focus on specialized subjects is strengthened, and their motives for professional activity are reinforced. Interest in scientific research increases, and the characteristics of the chosen profession are studied. Simultaneously, students' social activity develops, and their level of self-organization improves.

The professional readiness stage (fourth year) is linked to the attitude towards pedagogical activity and encourages the mastery of specialist work methods and technologies. At this stage, students approach the choice of practice location for acquiring pedagogical experience more consciously.

When applying innovative educational technologies, it is important to study the subject teacher's information and communication competence and ways to organize their professional activities. The text also describes innovative educational technologies implemented in future teachers' professional training, the use of traditional, non-traditional, interactive, and modern educational technologies in organizing practical classes, as well as approaches for organizing the subject teacher's professional activities in implementing competency-based lessons.

In modern conditions, it is advisable to use innovative forms of education to enhance students' learning activities and improve the quality and effectiveness

of teaching. Today, practical games, problem-based learning, interactive learning, modular credit system, distance learning, blended learning, and master classes are recognized as innovative forms of education.

Problem-based learning technology (problem and problematic situation). The primary task of developmental educational technology, serving to implement the professional training of future teachers, is the problem-based educational approach.

Problem-based learning has three scientific and methodological aspects:

1. Creating a problematic situation.
2. Formulating the problem.
3. Finding a solution to the problem.

A problematic situation can be created in all types of training sessions. How often it is formed during the lesson depends on the teacher. The significance of a problematic situation lies in the fact that it focuses students' attention on one area (the problem) and teaches students to research and think critically.

Problem-based learning involves creating a problematic situation under the teacher's guidance, and this problem entails organizing an educational process that allows students to creatively master theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and abilities as a result of their active, independent activity, and develop intellectual capabilities.

In the process of problem-based learning, students are given assignments to analyze research, heuristic, and problematic situations, which may include: - formulating tasks; - dealing with an unformed question; - working with excess information; - making independent generalizations based on their own practical observations; - describing the essence of an object without using instructions; - determining the boundaries and levels of application of the obtained results; - identifying the mechanism of a phenomenon's manifestation; - completing tasks such as "instant" problem-solving. - It is possible to give assignments such as finding "one instant."

The algorithm for reaching a solution in problematic situations is implemented in the following order: setting the problem, collecting data, processing the information, defining a solution model, gathering additional information and incorporating it into the chosen solution model, identifying contradictions between the new data and the solution model, resolving the contradiction, and creating a new solution model.

The "problem situation" method is a method aimed at developing students' skills in analyzing the causes and consequences of problematic situations and finding solutions to them.

The complexity of the problem chosen for the "problem situation" method should correspond to the level of knowledge of the students. They must be able to find a solution to the problem, otherwise failing to find a solution will lead to a loss of interest among students and a loss of self-confidence. When using the "problem situation" method, students learn to think independently, analyze the causes and consequences of the problem, and find a solution to it. The stages of the "problem situation" method: - the teacher selects a problem situation on the topic, defines goals and objectives. The instructor explains the problem to the students; - the instructor introduces the students to the goals, objectives, and conditions of the assignment; - the instructor divides the students into small groups; - small groups study the given problem situation.

They identify the causes of the problem and each group makes a presentation. After all the presentations, the same thoughts are summarized.

At this stage, they present their opinions on the consequences of the problem. The same thoughts are summarized after the presentation.

2. Discuss and analyze various possibilities for solving the problem. They develop ways to solve a problematic situation.

3. Small groups present a solution to a problem situation and propose their own options.

4. After all the presentations, the same solutions are summarized. The group, together with the teacher, selects the most optimal options for solving the problem situation.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, in the development of the learner's personality, it is necessary, first and foremost, to ensure the memorization of learning materials based on the strengthening of their perception and memory. To achieve the lesson's goal, it is important to consider the level of students' knowledge, correctly select learning materials, pay serious attention to equipment, and correctly select and apply the necessary methods and techniques to make the learning materials understandable.

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